

Correct location for FNAC-Breast Biopsy

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Abstract

Approximately 2.3 million women worldwide were diagnosed with breast cancer. Breast cancer is a type of cancer that form in the cells of the breast[1]. Breast cancer diagnosis typically involves a combination of clinical evaluation, Imaging tests and biopsy. Breast cancer biopsy is a medical procedure involves removing a small sample of tissue or cell from the breast examine for cancer cells[2]. There are many different types of biopsies (Incisional biopsy, Core needle biopsy, U/S guided biopsy and Fine needle aspiration cytology)[3].FNAC is a diagnostic procedure used to investigate lumps or masses under the skin including breast lumps and thyroid nodules. FNAC location issues refer to the challenges and limitation of performing FNAC biopsy on lesions or masses located in difficult to access areas of the breast. In FNAC procedure a thin sterile needle usually 22-25 gauge is inserted into the skin and guided to the target lesion[4]. The needle is attached to a syringe and gentle suction is applied to aspirate cells from lesion. Needle location issues in FNAC refer to challenges and limitation of accurately placing the needle in target lesion during procedure in order to place accurate needle the external measurement of breast by vernier caliper can be used [5].

Accurate Measurement for placing Needle in FNAC

To place and accurate needle, the following can be used:

Ultrasound & Breast quadrant localization:

Ultrasound is a valuable tool for identifying and locating breast lesion and measuring the diameter of lesion using ultrasound measurement calibration including determining the breast quadrant where the lesion is located[6].

Fig: 1.1

The breast is typically divided into 4 quadrants:

- **Upper outer quadrant:**
The area above the nipple and to the outside of the breast
- **Upper inner quadrant:**
The area above the nipple and to the inside of the breast

- **Lower outer quadrant:**
The area below the nipple and to the outside of the breast
- **Lower inner quadrant:**
The area below the nipple and to the inside of the breast

Fig: 1.2

To localize a breast lesion using ultrasound the following steps are typically taken[7]:

1. Patient position
2. Ultrasound probe placement
3. Lesion identification
4. Quadrant localization

After localizing a breast lesion to a specific quadrant the next step typically involve a marking the skin[8].

Fig: 1.3

Vernier Caliper Measurement for placing accurate needle

A vernier caliper is a precision measuring instrument used to measure the distance between two points. There are three main components of a vernier caliper[9]:

- **Main scale:**
The main scale is the long, fixed scale on their caliper.
- **Vernier scale:**
The vernier is the short, sliding scale on the caliper.
- **Jaws:**
The jaws are the two movable parts of the caliper that come into contact with the object being measured.

To measure the breast diameter for placing an accurate needle using a vernier caliper follow these steps:

- Place a vernier caliper jaws on the either side of the skin marking ensuring they are parallel to each other and perpendicular to the surface[10].

Fig: 1.4

- Gently close the caliper jaws until the vernier scale show the diameter of lesion which is obtain from ultrasound[12].

Fig: 1.5

- After vernier caliper reading marking the skin in a specific area where the vernier caliper scale show exact diameter of lesion [13].

Fig: 1.6

Insertion of needle

After vernier caliper measurement a fine needle is inserted into the skin marking area and aspirate (Suck out) cells and fluid from the lump or mass using a syringe. Needle is withdrawn and pressure is applied to the site to prevent bleeding[14].

Fig 1.7

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